

PORTRAIT OF A RESEARCHER:

Gabriel Merino

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10719169

"Do the best you can until you know better. Then when you know better, do better."

Date of birth: August 10, 1975
Position: Full Professor. Centro de Investigación y de Estudios Avanzados Unidad Mérida (Cinvestav Mérida)
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Education: Ph. D. in Chemistry

Awards: Moshinsky Medal (Institute of Physics, UNAM, 2019), Walter Kohn Prize (International Centre for Theoretical Physics, 2018), Andrés Manuel del Río Award (Sociedad Química de México, 2017), Mexican Academy of Sciences Award (Exact Sciences Academia Mexicana de Ciencias, 2012)

Current research: Computational Chemistry, Hypercoordination, Aromaticity, Chemical Bond.

Published papers: Around 200

Hobbies: Foodie and Music

1.) What do you consider your greatest achievement?

Consolidate an active and competitive research group where different and eclectic ideas are developed.

2.) How do you celebrate success?

Have a drink and go out for a dinner.

3.) What was your worst nightmare?

Bureaucracy has been and is my worst nightmare.

4.) What makes you lose track of time?

Programming and writing. In both activities I can spend a

Prof. Gabriel Merino, third from left in the back row.

lot of time.

5.) What is the best advice you've ever given?

Do the best you can until you know better. Then when you know better, do better.

6.) What's the worst advice you've ever given?

It does not matter.

7.) What's your favorite food?

I like to test all kind of food. The best for me is the Italian, Spanish, and Mexican food.

8.) What are your favorite pieces of music?

Jazz, rock, and blues.

10.) What was the most significant scientific advance in the last century?

Quantum mechanics.

11.) Do you have a favorite saying?

"El que es perico, donde quiera es verde"

12.) What is the biggest problem that scientists face today?

Big data, artificial intelligence, or machine learning tools allow us to predict the behavior of nature. However, good results can be obtained just if the models and data are correct and in many cases, such models are incomplete and we know just a very small part of the total data.

13.) What is your favorite piece of research?

Any piece of research that comes out of a genuine question, even if it's not in vogue today, is worth it.

14.) Do you have a favorite place on earth?

Each country has beautiful places. Venice, Prague, Florence, San Sebastian, Cuetzalan, ..., and of course Mérida and Puebla.

15.) What was your most exciting discovery?

I guess the most important contributions of my group are the studies in planar hypercoordinate carbon molecules, the discovery of fluxionality in boron clusters, and the development of new computational tools to study aromaticity and kinetics.

16) Why did you choose chemistry?

That is a long story. Originally I was planning to study archeology. However, participating in the Chemistry Olympiad changed my life.

17) If you weren't a scientist, what would you be?

Archeologist.

18) What is your secret / or not-so-secret passion?

Archeology, history, math, and of course food.

20) Do you notice a difference in computational chemistry research now and at the beginning of your career?

I had my first contact with theory in 1996. Any molecule with more than 30 atoms was almost impossible to compute by quantum chemical methods, so bulky substituents were changed by hydrogen atoms or methyl groups. Now, we can compute big systems using bigger basis sets, including dispersion, relativistic effects, etc. So, now we have more precision and numbers closest to

the experiment. This simulated reality is really noticeable. However, this is frequently accompanied by a lack of understanding -understanding in chemical terms- of how computations give such results. So, predicting properties not necessarily imply physical and chemical phenomena comprehension. Robert Parr summarizes it with one phrase: "To calculate is not to understand". So, finally, we have differences in Computational Chemistry, but the objective is the same; it is to understand the behavior of chemical entities.

21) What is the secret to publishing high-impact articles?

Several articles summarize possible recipes or algorithms for writing a fruitful manuscript. I think the most important thing is to write a story as best we can.

22) Could you list the 5 most important articles of your career and why?

1) S. Pan, J. Barroso, S. Jalife, T. Heine, K. Asmis, G. Merino "Fluxional Boron Clusters: From Theory to Reality" *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2019**, *52*, 2732.

Here we summarized our contributions about fluxional boron clusters. This topic is exciting because we suggested such dynamical behavior in 2010 and six year later it was supported by IR experiments in B13+.

2) E. Dzib, J. L Cabellos, F. Ortíz-Chi, S. Pan, A. Galano, G. Merino "Eyringpy: A Program for Computing Rate Constants in the Gas Phase and in Solution" *Int. J. Quantum Chem.* **2019**, *119*, e25686.

Eyringpy is our new program for computing kinetic parameters of a reaction.

3) V. Vassilev-Galindo, S. Pan, K. J. Donald, G. Merino "Planar pentacoordinate carbons" *Nat. Rev. Chem.* **2018**, *2*, 114.

Everything about planar pentacoordinate carbon atoms is summarized in this contribution.

4) R. Islas, T. Heine, G. Merino "The induced magnetic field" *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2012**, *45*, 215.

We suggested an pictorial way to diagnose aromaticity based on the induced magnetic field.

5) G. Merino, M. A. Méndez-Rojas, A. Vela "(C₅M₂-n)_n- (M = Li, Na, K, and n = 0, 1, 2). A new family of molecules containing planar tetracoordinate carbons" *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2003**, *125*, 6026.

Our first contribution in planar tetracoordinate carbon chemistry.

23) What advice would you give to young people who decided to be a chemist?

Any researcher must choose a new idea and develop it, regardless of whether it is a hot topic or not, the important thing is to answer your question.